

Integrated bibliography of publications and online resources on Albanian Lepidoptera.

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Abstract

Albania's butterfly fauna has been increasingly documented over the past century, with research evolving from early descriptive studies to comprehensive modern investigations. The *Fluturat e Shqipërisë* website consolidates this growing body of work, integrating scientific publications, checklists, and monitoring data into a single resource.

In this publication, the referenced sources are systematically organized chronologically and alphabetically, reflecting the multidisciplinary and international scope of Lepidoptera research relevant to Albania and supporting ongoing scientific and conservation efforts.

Key words

Albania, Lepidoptera, data compilation, bibliography, online resources, Fluturat e Shqipërisë.

Introduction

Research on the butterfly fauna of Albania began in the early 20th century, with the earliest published contributions primarily authored by Prof. H. Rebel

A more sustained scientific interest developed after 1990, notably through the work of the late Prof. K. Misja, as well as contributions by S. Abadjiev and S. Beshkov, who laid important groundwork for the documentation of Albania's Lepidoptera.

In recent years, the documentation of butterfly diversity in Albania has increased substantially, resulting in numerous publications and data sources covering taxonomy, distribution, ecology, and conservation. The website *Fluturat e Shqipërisë* compiles and integrates this growing body of literature, providing a centralized resource based on scientific articles, faunal checklists and biodiversity monitoring platforms.

The following list includes all sources referenced in the development of *Fluturat e Shqipërisë*, arranged chronologically and alphabetically by author or institutional source. It reflects the multidisciplinary and international scope of current Lepidoptera research relevant to the Albanian fauna.

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Conclusion

This bibliography aims to offer the most complete overview to date of published and digital resources concerning the butterflies of Albania.

It acknowledges the valuable contributions of all researchers whose work has advanced the understanding of the country's Lepidoptera.

To ensure ongoing accuracy and completeness, *Fluturat e Shqipërisë* remains open to updates and welcomes additional references that may have been overlooked or are newly published.

Author contributions

Both authors were equally involved in all stages of the research process, from conceptualization through data analysis, to drafting and revising the manuscript.

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We acknowledge the foundational work of early researchers who initiated the study of Albania's Lepidoptera. Their initial documentation provided a basis for continued scientific investigation. We also recognize the sustained efforts of subsequent authors and researchers whose publications have significantly contributed to expanding knowledge on the biodiversity of butterflies in Albania. Their collective work has been essential in building the current comprehensive understanding of the region's Lepidoptera fauna and continue to inspire ongoing research and conservation in Albania's rich natural heritage.